

Data Competence Centre for Natural Science Collections
and Object-Related Research

Preparing WiNoDa Learning Events: Guidelines for Instructors

(Version 3.2, September 2025)

Dear Instructors,

Thank you for your support of the WiNoDa Knowledge Lab! The lab thrives on the vibrant community and many knowledge exchange formats – including your learning event. We are sure it will be a great success. Let's get there together!

To help establish shared standards for high-quality teaching, we've prepared this guide as a reference. Our aim is to support you as effectively as possible in designing learning materials and organizing educational events.

Who are we?

- WiNoDa is a space for **non-hierarchical, participatory** learning and research, built on a vibrant community. Formal academic hierarchies play no role within WiNoDa.
- We value and promote a diversity of scientific perspectives and research questions. **Multidisciplinarity** is consciously embraced as an asset.
- We place strong emphasis on ethical aspects of data science and research, fostering **transparency** and a **constructive approach to dealing with mistakes**.

What are our goals?

The WiNoDa Knowledge Lab pursues the following goals, which are significantly shaped by your contribution and teaching content:

- **Advancing Research:** Teaching data science skills with a strong focus on practical, hands-on competencies.
- **Connecting Expertise:** Fostering collaboration between museums and disciplines such as biodiversity research, archaeology, digital humanities – and data science.
- **Opening Up Science:** Promoting open science, public engagement, and cooperation between academic and non-academic actors.

Target groups: Who do we work for?

Our community is diverse and includes participants from a wide range of professional backgrounds: from doctoral researchers and postdocs to professors, data stewards, data managers, collection managers, curators, science communicators, as well as representatives from industry and public administration.

Regardless of their seniority, individuals within each group might differ in their knowledge on a particular topic (e.g., a professor in biology might not be familiar with some recent AI applications for scientific collections). Therefore, when designing your educational offer please discuss with your WiNoDa contact for which experience level the materials should be designed (**beginners, intermediate learners, or experts**).

It is essential to clearly communicate which level the content is designed for and what prior knowledge is required to make effective use of the learning opportunity; participants assign themselves to an experience level based on self-assessment.

To support your planning, we have created short descriptions of fictional personas that represent our community (see Appendix C of the *WiNoDa Quality Concept*).

Quality standards: What should I pay attention to?

Within the WiNoDa network, we strive for shared standards for scientific content, ethics, didactics, and language.

❖ Scientific content

The development and implementation of learning opportunities follow scientific standards and, where applicable, the guidelines for ensuring [Good Research Practice](#).

Interdisciplinarity: Our goal is to bring together researchers from various disciplines and foster exchange among them. To support this, we recommend formats and topics that encourage and facilitate cross-disciplinary collaboration.

❖ Didactics

Learning objectives for each session should be clearly defined and communicated to the WiNoDa team beforehand and to the learners at the beginning of the session. This allows participants to make an informed decision about attending, supports self-assessment of their progress, and enables meaningful evaluation of the course.

Practical relevance: Learning content should be directly applicable to the participants' professional or academic practice. Real-life examples that reflect concrete challenges from their daily work are always appreciated by the audience. These examples can also be provided by the participants themselves.

Interactive formats such as project-based work encourage exchange between participants from different disciplines. Learning modules should combine theoretical input with practical exercises, case studies, group work, and discussions to meet the diverse needs of the participants.

❖ Ethics

[Good Research Practice](#), along with the **FAIR and CARE principles**, is at the core of our learning offers. We raise awareness of the challenges in the field of Open Science and emphasize the responsible handling of data.

WiNoDa aims to build an open, multidisciplinary community rooted in transparency and inclusion.

❖ Language and communication

The standard language for WiNoDa events is **English**; however, depending on the target audience, another language may be used. All learning materials should nonetheless be made available in an English version.

Inclusive language: WiNoDa is committed to building a non-hierarchical and inclusive community. Respectful interaction with all participants – regardless of gender, origin, abilities, or other characteristics – is essential. We use [inclusive](#)

[language](#) that is gender-sensitive and free from discriminatory expressions. This includes choosing terminology that promotes diversity and avoiding stereotypes or harmful wording. Instructors are free to decide how to apply inclusive language, though we recommend using gender-sensitive phrasing.

We also encourage designing materials with **accessibility** in mind and recommend indicating when content has been adapted for individuals with specific needs. This includes considerations for visual or hearing impairments, color blindness, motor limitations, and cognitive differences. Additionally, learning materials should be provided in accessible PDF format whenever possible.

❖ Reuse of learning materials

The value of a learning event goes beyond the session itself – it also lies in the materials it generates. We aim to document and make successful courses or training **accessible online** so that others can benefit from them as well. We therefore appreciate your support in sharing slides, training datasets, code files, or any other materials that can contribute to further learning. If your session is a demo including coding, we suggest sharing the code script with the participants beforehand, so that they can follow along in real time.

Suggestions for designing your learning session

Based on feedback gathered from participants of previous events, we have compiled a brief list of suggestions for designing educational materials and presentations in online events.

Slide design: “A picture is worth a thousand words.” While an exaggeration, this saying holds some truth, especially for online events. Participants can feel overwhelmed or distracted by walls of text, whereas photos and graphs help them focus on the speaker’s words. Whenever possible, consider replacing text with images or splitting text across multiple slides.

Content quantity and speed: Tailoring your presentation to the available time allows you to speak at a comfortable pace, giving the audience the chance to fully grasp your points. As a rule of thumb, we suggest having no more than one slide per minute of speaking time. This does not mean you must spend exactly one minute per slide, but it helps keep your presentation concise and manageable. Consider also including short intervals for questions during your talk, so participants can clarify points before you build on them further.

Presentation delivery: Besides speaking at a comfortable speed, try to deliver your talk with enthusiasm for the topic – your energy will spark curiosity and engagement among participants. Having a script is fine, but reading it word-for-word can make it difficult for the audience to follow. Aim for a natural, conversational delivery.

Connection, setting, and technical aspects: Please ensure you present from a location with a stable internet connection and minimal background noise. If you plan to share your screen while using software such as R or QGIS, let your WiNoDa contact know in advance so they can schedule a Zoom test session, as compatibility issues may arise.

Evaluation

WiNoDa staff will support you throughout the entire process, from the planning and preparation phase to the conclusion of your course, and will convey to you the feedback we collect from participants. This information is also used internally to continuously improve the quality of our learning offers.

We use the following standardized questions for participants:

1. *The course provided clear learning objectives and was well-structured and comprehensive.*
2. *I felt at ease, seen, and welcome in the course.*
3. *My knowledge increase is... (from "very low" to "very high")*
4. *I remember the core aspects of the course topics and can briefly summarize the content of the course.*
5. *I feel able to apply what I have learned in my research.*
6. *The course was relevant to my work and met my expectations.*
7. *The materials provided in the course were relevant and of high quality.*
8. *The course motivated me to engage more with the topics covered.*
9. *There was sufficient time for discussion and immediate feedback during the course.*
10. *The pace of the course was appropriate (not too fast, not too slow).*

Again, thank you for your contribution! We are looking forward to hosting your learning event!

Do you have any questions or need further support?

If so, please contact us: winoda@gfbio.org

Impressum

WiNoDa Knowledge Lab – Data Competence Center for Natural Science Collections and Object-Related Research

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For more information about the WiNoDa Knowledge Lab, visit www.winoda.de

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